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School Environmental Variables and Academic Performance of Student Nurses in Family Health Nursing in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the difference in school variables on the academic performance of students in family health course in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all year two and three student nurses offering family health nursing (2022/2023 session). Three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted an ex-post facto design. Stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting 219 respondents. Two instruments tagged "School environment questionnaire" (SEQ) and "Family Health Achievement Test" (FHAT) were used to gather data. The instruments were face-validated by two experts: one from test and measurement and evaluation, and the other from the institute of education, University of Uyo. Data collected were analysed using independent t-test and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics. The results show critical t-value of 1.96 and a calculated t-value of 0.67 to 4.83; hence, the null hypotheses were rejected. The results further indicated significant differences in school location, teacher-student relationship, and availability of facilities/instructional materials for students in family health course. It was recommended, among others, that facilities/instructional materials should be adequately provided in order to improve academic performance of student nurses in the schools of nursing; and that there should be an improvement in the level of teacher-student relationship.

Keyword: school environmental variables, schools of nursing, family health, student nurses' performance in Akwa Ibom state

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Introduction

A careful look at student nurses' achievements in the family health nursing examination has shown considerable and progressive deterioration. The experiences of the teachers of family health nursing confirm this observation. Thus, this problem is considered serious enough that the Director of Nursing Services called for a general meeting involving all the principals of the schools to deliberate on this all-important issue. The results of this course (from 2018 to 2022) confirm this observation. Consequent upon the observed deterioration in students' academic achievement in family health nursing, the feeling is that several factors contributed to this; among them include such variables as school location, class size, student-teacher relationship, and availability of facilities and learning materials.

Family health nursing as we know it today evolved in the 1970s, when nurses began to consider health promotion, in addition to illness care, as a legitimate concern for the nursing profession. Family health nursing has its roots in four specialties: community health nursing, maternal-child nursing, psychiatric/mental health nursing, and family nursing practitioners (Hanson, 2000). Family nursing search evolved with the family as the unit of the study rather than individual family members (Murphy, 2005). The dynamic nature of nursing theory and practice, health care delivery, related disciplines, nursing education curricula, health policy, and health care consumers in the past years has contributed greatly to the development of family health nursing as distinct from community health nursing (Bo Mar, 2008). Family nursing research has progressed in the past two decades from a focus on family dyads of mother and infant or husband and wife to a focus on the family as a unit (Gillis, 2003).

School location is also significant to the effectiveness of students' learning. This is because the distance of school location will determine the consistency and punctuality of students' attendance at school. Some students will prefer to enrol in a school that is closer to their homes. It would make the students participate actively in school activities as well as improve their performance. Most parents, especially those with low incomes who cannot afford transportation costs for their children, will prefer suburban schools (Onyehalu, 2002).

It is essential to note that class size is one of the important factors that affect students' achievement at school. If the number of students assigned to a particular class is more than the specific size (30–40), it would definitely disrupt the effective

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management of the class by the teacher. According to Witing (2003), too many students congested in a small classroom will negatively affect the performance of students in that class. One of the characteristics of a conducive learning environment is the small class size assigned to a teacher at a time. Psychologically, students feel free and comfortable when they sit with an adequate class size (30 to 40 students) and improve their listening skills without much distraction.

The teacher's attitude towards teaching plays a very prominent role in the academic performance of the learners. Udoukpong and Okon (2005) noted that classroom teaching, which is influenced by the attitude of the teachers, is an extremely complex task often carried out in an extremely stressful work environment. Research on teaching has established that the key to successful classroom management is teachers' ability to maximise the time that students spend actively engaged in worthwhile activities (Brophy, 2008).

Considering instructional materials in any school subject in Nigeria, the teacher represents the most important aspect of the educational system. It is on the teacher that the implementation of the curriculum depends. Improvement in the quality of our educational system is the responsibility of teachers (Adaralegbe, 2000). Thus, drawing on the literature on the concept of teaching, the centrality of the variables in effective curriculum implementation can be gauged from one of the conclusions of the House of Common Select Committee Report (2006), which stated that skills of diagnosing learning success and difficulty and selecting and presenting new tasks are the essence of teachers' profession and vital to children's progress. This approach takes due account of the role of the learner in mediating and structuring knowledge and places even greater stress on teachers' competence in the subject matter. Several studies have noted the importance of the teacher-student relationship and the academic achievement of the students.

Statement of the Problem

Low performance by nurses in internal and external (council) examinations has been a source of concern to many teachers and parents. The students' relationships in class with their lecturers and other students have an adverse effect on their achievement in school. This live-along life habit is rather worse in the case of the student-teacher relationship in that it does not allow the students to be free with the teacher during teaching in the class, even after the class.

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In almost all the nursing schools in Akwa Ibom State, instructional materials, facilities, and equipment such as a demonstration room, a well-furnished library, electricity, tables, chairs, water supply, and toilets are inadequate. These could likely impede students from achieving the desired results in their various subjects, including family health courses. The researcher therefore undertakes this study to assess how these factors—availability of facilities and learning material, poor student-teacher relationships, and school location—contribute to students' academic achievement in family health nursing in the schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

This study examines the different environmental variables and student academic performance in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study aimed at the following objectives:

1. To examine the relationship between school location and student academic performance in family health nursing course in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.
2. To assess the difference in academic achievement based on the availability of facilities and learning materials for family health nursing course in the nursing schools in Akwa Ibom State.
3. To identify the relationship between the teacher-student relationship and the academic achievement of students in family health nursing in the school of nursing, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the difference in school location on students' academic achievement in family health nursing course in schools of nursing, Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the difference in availability of facilities/learning materials on students' academic achievement in family health nursing in schools of nursing, Akwa Ibom State?
3. What is the relationship between teacher-student relationship and the academic performance of students in family health nursing in schools of nursing, Akwa Ibom State?

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Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in school location on students' academic achievement in family health nursing in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in the availability of facilities/learning materials on students in family health nursing in schools of nursing, Akwa Ibom State.
3. There is no significant relationship between teacher-student relationships and students' academic performance in family health nursing in schools of nursing.

Conceptual Review

School Location and Academic Performance of Students

According to the statement of Geisinger (2006), school location is one of the major factors that determines frequent access to school. It contributes to students' lack of access and attendance in school lessons or classes, as in some of the nursing schools located in suburban areas where students will be leaving the school to get pocket money from the parents. In certain areas of the world, it is more difficult for students to get to school. For example, in high-latitude areas of India or in some interior parts of Akwa Ibom State, severe weather conditions for more than seven months of the year make school attendance erratic and force students to remain at home (Postiglione).

In those remote locations, Dowel (2001) supported the idea that insufficient school funds contribute to low attendance rates by creating undesirable and unsafe learning environments for students. That is why some students play frequently without permission. They leave the class without the official permission of the class tutor, saying that they are going home. Due to the distance between the home and the school, they sometimes feel relaxed and unmotivated to go to school. In 1996, the General Accounting Office (GAO) reported that poor conditions existed in many rural communities; one out of every school had at least one inadequate structural or mechanical feature. In this situation where regular school attendance is rare, a low population contributes to the problem. In other locations, large numbers are often the cause of low attendance rates.

In a study examining the correlation between location and school attendance and attainment in Argentina and Panama, researchers found that urban residence was positively correlated with school attendance and attainment, but another study in a Louisiana school district found that schools with the lowest attendance rates were in

metropolitan areas. Several studies, according to Munillan (2005), affirm that geographical location affects school attendance, but no matter where a child or student lives, there is evidence that location will contribute to a child's access and attendance to education. If attendance is affected, certainly, active participation is hindered; if active participation is affected, it means that his performance will be low.

Availability of Facilities/Learning Materials and Students Academic Performance

Salawa and Sampson (2002) opined that the availability of teaching aids in schools is very pertinent to educational development, both for the child who learns and for the educational system. A school without sufficient instructional aids would produce low performance from their students in class lessons and in their chosen career subjects. It becomes necessary for a teacher to properly prepare a selection of instructional facilities for teaching and learning. Richards and Wills (2001) claimed that adequate preparation and selection of facilities and media is a professional instinct that would put the teacher in an advantaged position towards effective delivery of the lesson. In teaching family health to the students in nursing schools, it is only proper if the teacher comes to the class with a teaching aid, e.g., a well-labelled diagram of a human being for motivational illustration. Of course, students get more motivated and excited by what they see than by what they hear. What they see enhances understanding more than what they hear (Witting and Williams, 2003).

To understand certain terms in family health, objects or models (e.g., a skeletal structure of a human being) are necessary to present or demonstrate in the course of teaching. But when those aids are not available, it makes teaching or lessons boring and less interesting. There is evidence that when instructional facilities are frequently utilised by the teacher and the students, there will be good performance by both the teachers and the students (Onyehalu, 2002). Availability of relevant instructional aids and their usage are inevitable in the teaching process, as this would help the teacher limit talk and abstract discussion. However, the effectiveness of teacher/learning lies in the availability and teacher's capacity to effectively select or prepare instructional materials that have special abilities to appeal to the sense of hearing and seeing of the learner and also attract and improve attention. According to Nacino (2003), the teacher who always utilises the available instructional materials is bound to be proficient in the lesson delivery and hence improve the students' achievement in that subject. During new lesson

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planning, the teacher develops innovative ideas about the types of instructional materials available that could be used or improvised, which would positively impact the learners.

The availability of facilities such as electricity, water supply, and a good toilet will enhance high academic performance of student nurses. But on the other hand, the epileptic nature of light in nursing schools can pose a great problem to academic performance. In a situation in which a student will walk some kilometers to fetch water every day for his or her daily needs, such a time should have been used for studying. Hostel accommodation is also a problem. For instance, six students are in a small room, which does not allow them enough space to read adequately at night. The library is not spacious and well furnished with current books, journals, and other materials related to the profession and other fields of endeavour. In this era of technology (ICT), the schools of nursing have no functional computer systems or units for training students in this regard. The number of tutors in relation to the student ratio is grossly inadequate. In concrete terms, ICT has enhanced teaching and learning through its dynamic interactive mode of presentation.

Teacher-Student Relationship with Students Academic Performance

A good teacher-student relationship plays an important role in directing students into success and achievement of their goals for elementary, secondary, and higher institutions (Checkering and Gambson, 2002). Given the importance of students' learning, most of the research students in the area have emphasised students' involvement with the teacher. Personally, or privately, students meet a teacher and complain about academic issues that he or she is not aware of or that there is no convenient time to ask the teacher in the class. Sometimes, the student goes to the staffroom to meet with the teacher at leisure. This provides a great opportunity for the teacher to show great concern and spend more time explaining a point of the lesson taught more clearly than was done in the general class. At times, teachers do interact with the students on other educational issues, depending on how sound the student is academically. Frequently, it is done with the class captain (Deberard and Spielmaus, 2004).

Lamoure and James (2000) noted that students who show closeness to the teacher are bold students. Such students always take a bold step and have enthusiasm to

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approach the teacher for educational discussion. This discussion could lead to students acquiring more knowledge about the usefulness of a particular subject in their chosen career. Further, discussion may propel the student to perform well academically and motivate him to learn to actualize his chosen career in the future.

Evidence has shown that the quality of student-teacher relations at school has a great effect on student educational attainment. Effective learning demands that students, from time to time, meet with their lesson teacher to discuss personal and academic weaknesses with him. The teachers create time for students to express their complaints to them when they are free. (Umbach and Wawrzynski, 2005).

The schools are an extension of the home since the socialisation process starts in the home and continues in the school. During the early years of the introduction of formal education in Nigeria, teachers were feared more by students than their parents. Students who misbehaved at home were reported by their parents to the teachers, and they were severely punished. At school, teachers were perfectly in control of the students, who submitted themselves completely to them. Teachers, on their part, devoted themselves to teaching the students and regarded the success of their students as their primary concern. They were more concerned about their students' success than the students themselves because society would judge them by the students' performance.

According to Udofot (2005), teacher personality is a major factor in school achievement. The teacher's teaching style, habits, language, and relationships with the learners and with his colleagues are essential components of the teacher's personality. A teacher who is academically sound, professionally competent, and committed is able to command the respect of the learner through good teaching. Learners under him would enjoy teaching and would not like to be absent from class in order not to miss teaching. In the same way, learners would hardly respect a teacher who is unkempt and wears unclean clothes, who goes to class drunk, and who uses abusive words on his colleagues and on the learners.

Methodology

Area of the Study

The area of the study is Akwa Ibom State, one of the 36 Nigerian administrative divisions. The research work was conducted in four schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State. The four schools are located in Ikot Ekpene, Uyo, Eket, and Itukmbang. Akwa

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Ibom State has 31 local government areas, with the headquarters located at Uyo. In each of the local government areas cited, a hospital, a health centre, or a health facility, and a university teaching hospital in Uyo, the capital city, are trained and qualified nurses. The state covers an area of 7,245,935 sq. km. and has an approximate population of 13 million people.

The School of Nursing in Ikot Ekpene is located along Abak Road in Ikot Ekpene; Anua School of Nursing is situated in Anua village in Uyo, the capital city, along Anua Nsukara Road; the School of Nursing in Eket is sited along Park Road in Eket; and the School of Nursing Itukmbang is situated in Itukmbang village off km 30 airport road in Uruan.

Research Design

The design adopted in this study was ex-post-facto research design. This design was deemed appropriate because the researcher cannot manipulate the effect on the dependent variable but just obtains the effect already existing in the natural course of events. This research design was found suitable for the study, as it attempted to find out the existing difference in the independent variables (school variables) on the dependent variable (students' academic performance) under investigation and the testing of hypotheses.

Population of the Study

The study population comprised all the year two and three students in all four schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State, which formed the target population for this study. The population size was 419, comprising 32 males and 387 females.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size was 210 student nurses selected through the stratified random sampling technique, representing 50% of the population in the study area. There are 128 students in Anua, 98 in Eket, and 103 in Itukmbang while Ikot Ekpene has 110 students, making up 419 students, being the number of all year two and three students (Data collected from the principals of each of the schools).

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Table 1: Sampling frame used for data collection

S/N	School Code	Total	NO. of Respondents 50%
1	001	108	54
2	002	110	55
3	003	103	52
4	004	98	49
	Total	419	210

(001 Anua, 002 Ikot Ekpene, 003 Itukmbang, 004 Eket)

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The data obtained were coded and entered into a spread sheet for analysis. Hypotheses one, two, and three were tested using an independent t-test, while hypothesis three was tested using the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to determine the difference in school variables and academic performance of the students in family health nursing. Mean scores were calculated for each of the variables.

Data Analysis, Results, and Discussion of Findings

Ho₁, There is a significant difference in the school location on academic performance of students in schools of nursing in urban and rural areas of Akwa Ibom State.

In other to test for the null hypothesis, the means and standard deviation obtained from the independent t-test scores of the two variables are presented in Table 2. The result shows that there is a difference in means scores of 55.2703 between the urban and rural scores of 53.5317.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis of Difference in School Location on Students' Academic Performance in family Health Nursing in Schools of Nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

Variable	n	Mean score	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit
Urban	74	55.2703	12.41	208	3.7	1.96
Rural	126	53.5317	11.40			

From the table, the t-calculated value is 3.7. This value was tested for significance by comparing it with the critical t-value (1.96) at .05 level with 208 degrees of freedom. The calculated t-value of (3.7) was greater than the t-value of (1.96). This implies that there is a significant difference in the academic performance of student nurses based on their school location.

Ho₂, There is a significant difference in the availability of facilities/learning materials on students' academic achievement in family health course in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

To test for the null hypothesis, the means and standard deviation obtained from the independent t-test scores of two variables are presented in Table 3. The result indicates that there is a difference in means scores between adequate instructional materials (55.8025) and inadequate instructional materials (52.215).

Summary of Independent t-test Analysis of the Difference in the Academic Performance of students with adequate instructional facilities/materials and those with inadequate instructional facilities/materials

Variable	n	Mean score	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit
Adequate	129	55.8025	11.93	208	2.14	1.96
Inadequate	81	52.215	11.13			

From the table, the t-calculated value is 2.14. This value was tested for a significant difference by comparing it with the critical t-value (1.96) at the 0.5 level with 208 degrees of freedom. The calculated t-value (2.14) was greater than the critical value (1.96). From the analysis, it was observed that students taught with adequate instructional facilities perform better than their counterparts taught with inadequate instructional facilities. The result implies that the mean difference between the two variables has a significant difference in the academic performance of students based on the availability of facilities/learning materials in the schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

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Ho3 There is a significant correlation between the teacher-student relationship and academic performance in family health nursing.

To test for the null hypothesis, the mean and the calculated r-values obtained from the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis is presented in Table 4. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the two variables under investigation.

Table 4: The Relationship between Teachers-Students Relationship on Students' Academic Performance in family health course In Schools of Nursing Akwa Ibom State

Variable	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	R-cal	r-crit
	$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Teachers-student	3020	45465	32569	0.67	0.139
Academic performance	11340	25638			

From the table, the critical value of t at $\alpha=0.05$ was 0.139; the calculated r-value 0.67 is greater than the critical value. The null hypothesis, H_{03} , is therefore rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the teacher-student relationship. In other words, teacher-student relationship enhances good academic performance in schools of nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of the Findings

Academic Performance of the Student Nurses Based on School Location

The result of the data analysis in table 2 was significant due to the fact that the calculated t-value (3.7) was greater than the critical t-value (1.96) at .05 levels with 208 degrees of freedom. This result implies that there is a significant difference in school location on students' academic performance in family health in schools of Nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

The significance of the result is in agreement with the opinion of Geisinger (2001), who stated that school location is one of the major factors that determines frequent access to school by the student. It was also in agreement with the opinion of Macmillan (2005), who affirmed that geographical location affects class attendance. But

no matter where a child or student lives, there is evidence that location will contribute to his/her access and attendance to education. The significance of the result caused the null hypothesis to be rejected while the alternative was accepted.

Academic Performance of Student Nurses Based on Teacher-Student Relationship

The result of the data analysis in table 3 was significant due to the fact that the calculated r-value (0.67) was greater than the critical r-value (0.139) at 0.05 levels, with 208 degrees of freedom. This result implies that there is a significant influence of teacher-student relationship on students' academic performance in family Health in schools of Nursing, Akwa Ibom State.

The significance of the result is in agreement with the opinion of Lamour and James (2000), who noted that students who show closeness to the teacher are bold students. Such students always take bold steps with enthusiasm to approach the teacher for educational discussion. It was also in agreement with the opinion of Udofot (2005), who asserted that teachers' personality is a major factor in school achievement. The teachers' teaching style, his habit, language and his relationship with the learners and his colleagues are essentials components of the teachers' personality. With this, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative was accepted.

Academic Performance of Student Nurses Based on the Availability of Facilities and Instructional Materials

The result of the data analysis in table 4 was significant due to the fact that the calculated t-value (4.83) was greater than the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 levels with 208 degrees of freedom. This result implies that there is a significant difference in class size on students' academic performances in family health in schools of Nursing in Akwa Ibom State.

The significance of the result is in agreement with the opinion of Reiser (2001), who asserted that the class unit is the basic unit of organisation for instruction; therefore, class size information should be foundational knowledge for educators. It was also in agreement with the opinion of Mosteller (2009), whose finding revealed that increasing class size has negative effects on students' achievement. The significance of the result caused the null hypothesis to be rejected while the alternative was accepted.

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Conclusions

Based on the findings of the research, the researcher draws the following conclusions:

1. School location contributes immensely to the student's academic performance in Family Health nursing that the academic performance of students in urban schools differs significantly from that of their counterparts in the rural schools.
2. Good teacher-student relationship contributes significantly to good academic performance of the students in Family Health.
3. Adequate class size is suitable for good academic performance of students as it encourages effective learning among the students.
4. When facilities/instructional materials needed by the students are put in place, student's academic performance in Family Health in schools of Nursing is guaranteed.

Recommendations and Implications

1. Since school location is one of the major factors that determine students' academic performance, schools should be located in a conducive environment with good road network. Besides, Government should give equal opportunity and instructional facilities to both urban and rural schools.
2. For a greater learning and higher academic performance in Family Health, teachers should create a good admmissive environment to their students so that the students can have easy access to them when there is need for that.
3. For students' academic performance to be effective, schools of Nursing should be well equipped with facilities, and instructional materials must be in school to make life bearable and to enhance learning.

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